

Effects of reporting levels on team workers in new business sectors

Wickramasinghe, V.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

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Abstract

The literature provides evidence for the effects of number of reporting levels on employees' attitudes, and in turn their reactions to work and work context. Yet, so far, little empirical attention has been paid to understand implications of the number of reporting levels on employees. The study investigated the differential effects of number of reporting levels on employees in teams in terms of opportunities for promotion, opportunities for lateral transfer, satisfaction with work environment, and team process. Survey methodology was used and 281 respondents who fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study responded. To examine the hypothesized relationships logistic regression was performed. The findings supported the hypothesis that employees perceive more opportunities for promotion when many reporting levels (3 to 5 in the present study) exist. Further, the findings supported the hypothesis that employees perceive more satisfaction with the work environment when few reporting levels (2 in the present study) exist.

Keywords: lateral transfer; promotion; reporting levels; team process; team work.

Introduction

In response to increasing global competition the business world has witnessed an emergence of new forms of organizations in recent years. For instance, due to the growing pervasiveness of information technology, developed countries in the West (North America, Europe and the Asia Pacific) have offshore outsourced research and development centres overseas or sent their programming, engineering, and technical back office work overseas taking the advantage of lower costs and broader talent pools around the world. Further,

organizations with project-based work structures have intensified in recent years to respond to highly differentiated and customized nature of demand in certain industries, such as creative and cultural, high technology, and professional and consulting (Turner & Keegan, 1999).

Irrespective of the nature of business, an organization structure provides structural foundation within which organizations function (Andersen & Jonsson, 2006; Cummings & Berger, 1976; Jacob, 2007). Jackson and Morgan (1982) viewed organization structure as durable arrangements within an organization since it shows the allocation of work roles and administrative mechanism that creates a pattern of interrelated work activities, and allows the organization to conduct, coordinate, and control its work activities. The complexity of an organization's structure in terms of the number of levels in the hierarchy is identified as vertical complexity or vertical differentiation, i.e., how pointed or flat the pyramid is (Andersen & Jonsson, 2006). This hierarchical structure is important in instrumental and social terms (Inzerilli & Laurent, 1983). In instrumental terms, organizational positions and relationships among positions are defined in terms of tasks or functions that are instrumental to the achievement of organizational objectives. In social terms, organizational positions and relationships among positions are defined in terms of social status and authority in the hierarchy (Inzerilli & Laurent, 1983).

When the number of reporting levels is identified as one of structural characteristics of any organization's anatomy that provides structural foundation within which organizations function (Cummings and Berger, 1976), this feature can influence attitudes and behaviours of employees who are exposed to it (Cummings and Berger, 1976). However, a limited number of previous conceptual and empirical studies provide evidence for the effect of reporting levels on employees' attitudes (e.g., Blau, 1968; Cummings & Berger, 1976; Porter & Lawler, 1964), and in turn their reactions to work and work context (e.g., Carzo & Yanouzas,

1969; Cummings & Berger, 1976; Oldham & Hackman, 1981). However, these studies are several decades old, and as a result these do not facilitate the generalisation of findings to the contemporary business world, especially to those business sectors that have emerged in the recent past. Although specific, well-defined jobs performed by individuals who work mostly independently of one another in bounded, stand-alone organisations continue to exist in the contemporary world of work, fundamental changes have occurred in the relationships among people, the work they do, and the organisations for which they do it (Oldham & Hackman, 2010). For instance, internal labour markets have become flatter implying that promotions are difficult to obtain and climbing up the hierarchy will be slower (Osterman, 2010). Further, developments in information and communications technology (ICT) have important implications for the way in which work is carried out (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010; Oldham & Hackman, 2010; Parker, Wall, & Cordery, 2001). Furthermore, there is an increasing prominence of work that is performed by teams rather than individuals. Employees may work in temporary teams, where membership shifts as work requirements change or they may serve on a project team (Oldham and Hackman, 2010). In this regard, the literature suggests that team-based work arrangements are highly favoured by contemporary organizations as one of the best means to achieve flexibility and versatility (Peters & Karren, 2009; Haas, 2010), and team work can occur in organizations with many as well as few reporting levels (Liyanaarachchi, 2011; Wickramasinghe, 2009). For instance, software development firms have a limited number of levels in the hierarchy and the work is organised around teams (Wickramasinghe, 2009). Telecommunication firms can have several levels in the organizational hierarchy with dual career ladders and work can be organised around either on-going or ad hoc teams of many types such as process improvement teams and quality circles (Liyanaarachchi, 2011). Therefore, it is important to understand the effect of number of reporting levels in the hierarchy or vertical complexity on employees working in teams,

placing the employee at the centre of analysis in contemporary work organizations. The findings of such studies appear to have implications for strategic decision making.

In the above context, by taking a sample of employees in team work environment, who are full-time engaged in newly emerged ICT related business sectors in Sri Lanka, the study investigated the differential effects of number of reporting levels on employees in terms of opportunities for promotion, opportunities for lateral transfer, team process, and satisfaction with work environment.

Review of Literature

Reporting levels

The term vertical complexity is used to describe the number of reporting levels in the hierarchy which decides whether an organization's shape is relatively tall or flat (Carzo & Yanouzas, 1969; Cummings & Berger, 1976). Yet, the literature suggests that there is no agreed measure to distinguish organizations with many reporting levels from those organizations with few reporting levels. For instance, Carzo and Yanouzas (1969) defined tall structure to have four reporting levels while flat structure to have two levels within any given organization's size category.

Some previous studies (such as Dalton et al., 1980; Urwick, 1956) suggest that the number of levels in the hierarchy and the span of control/supervision are closely related (Dalton et al., 1980; Urwick, 1956). Accordingly, with a given number of employees, relatively tall structure (with many reporting levels) must necessarily have a narrower span of control (few direct reports) while a relatively flat structure (with few reporting levels) would have a wider span of control (more direct reports) (Dalton et al., 1980). Some previous studies suggest that flatter structures create a potential for more effective supervision since energy, knowledge, time and abilities available for a supervisor is limited (e.g., Dalton et al.,

1980). However, in a recent study, Krasman (2014) found that span of control was not related to subordinates' perceptions of their supervisors' trustworthiness. Carillo & Kopelman (1991) provide evidence for a negative relationship between vertical complexity and productivity, where firms with least vertical complexity (one reporting level) were 44% more productive than those with the greatest complexity (five reporting levels).

In the present study, effects of reporting levels on employees in terms of four features of contemporary organizations, namely, promotions, lateral transfers, team process, and work environment, were investigated. In the following sections, the literature directly relevant in deriving hypotheses is reviewed in brief.

Effects of reporting levels on employees

Opportunities for promotion

There is an agreement on the meaning of the term “promotion” in the literature (Iverson & Roy, 1994; Peters, Greer, & Youngblood, 2000; Spilerman & Lunde, 1991). For instance, Peters et al. (2000, p. 274) define promotion as “the advancement of an individual from a particular position to one higher rank within the organizational hierarchy. An individual who receives a promotion usually has an increase in responsibility. In addition, a promotion is almost always associated with an increase in salary and organizational benefits”. According to Spilerman and Lunde (1991, p. 691), promotion refers to change of rank within an organization. Rank, or grade level, differentiates among workers with respect to status, power, and salary”. Iverson and Roy (1994, p. 20) define promotion as “the movement between different status levels within an organization”. Accordingly, employees who received promotions may experience increase in earnings and opportunities to acquire new capabilities while organizations will be able to retain their valuable employees. Therefore,

“opportunities for promotion” is an important feature for both employees and organizations alike.

With regard to the effect of reporting levels on opportunities for promotion, Blau (1968) found that organizations with many reporting levels had more explicit promotion regulations emphasizing merit rather than seniority. Porter and Lawler (1964) found that organizations with many reporting levels were better in producing security and the satisfaction of social needs. Wickramasinghe (2009, p. 427) stated that firms in information technology sector have about two layers in the hierarchy (i.e. top management and technical specialists), and as a consequence opportunities for promotion are few and far between. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H1: Opportunities for promotion will be higher when many reporting levels exist in the firm

Opportunities for lateral transfer

The literature identifies lateral transfers as scheduled non-merit upgrades, task re-organizations or job re-classifications (Schaefer, Massey, & Hermanson, 1979). Lateral transfers are not necessarily merit driven, usually do not involve substantial changes in compensation, and do not imply career advancement (Acosta, 2010). The literature further suggests that lateral transfers unlike promotions are relatively abundant in organizations (Acosta, 2010; Schaefer et al., 1979). Furthermore, although both promotions and lateral transfers increase the likelihood of a new lateral transfer in the future, previous lateral transfers do not affect the probability of being promoted in the future (Acosta, 2010).

The literature highlights the importance of lateral transfers to obtain a maximum output from employees (Schaefer et al., 1979). For instance, Schaefer et al. (1979) identified the importance of rotating employees across job positions, by way of lateral transfers, to

obtain the most from employees' capabilities. Based on the literature reviewed above on the connection between the number of reporting levels and the span of control (e.g., Dalton et al., 1980; Urwick, 1956), it is possible to assume that employees may receive more opportunities for lateral transfers when a fewer number of reporting levels exist in the firm. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2: Opportunities for lateral transfer will be lower when many reporting levels exist in the firm

Satisfaction with work environment

The literature implies that employees attached to organizations with few reporting levels seem to be more satisfied with their work environment than otherwise (Ghiselli & Johnson, 1970; Ivancevich & Donnelly, 1975; Porter & Lawler, 1964; Worthy, 1950). For instance, Worthy (1950) found that employees attached to organizations with few reporting levels had better morale than their counterparts attached to organizations at the opposite-end. Worthy (1950) recommended that firms should use fewer reporting levels with a wide span of supervision to achieve this advantage. Porter and Lawler (1964) found that organizations with a fewer reporting levels were better for self-actualization. Ivancevich and Donnelly (1975) found that absenteeism is low in organizations with a fewer reporting levels. Cummings and Berger (1976) reported that lower-level managers attached to organizations with a fewer reporting levels experience more need satisfaction than their counterparts attached to organizations at the opposite-end. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3: Employees' satisfaction with the work environment will be lower when many reporting levels exist in the firm

Team process

The term team process is used to refer to psychosocial outcomes of team work environment such as the degree of experienced friendliness, support, and ability to cope (Bourgault, Drouin, & Hamel, 2008; Staples & Webster, 2007; Wageman, Hackman, & Lehman, 2005). Literature provides evidence for the importance of many facets of team processes in team working environment (Bourgault et al., 2008; Staples & Webster, 2007; Wageman et al., 2005). For instance, Bourgault et al. (2008) describe the importance of the formalization of decision processes, team autonomy, and creating and sustaining a good team working environment. Staples and Webster (2007) describe team process using measures such as intention to remain in the team, ability to cope, and satisfaction with the team. Wageman et al. (2005) identify several indicators of team processes, such as satisfaction with within-team relationships, the quality of team task performance strategies, and the degree to which the team uses members' knowledge and skill. According to Wageman et al. (2005) these features of team process contribute positively to learning and well-being of individual team members, rather than frustrating, alienating, or de-skilling them.

Several previous studies suggest that firms with few reporting levels provide satisfying team context (such as Carillo and Kopelman, 1991; Ivancevich and Donnelly, 1975; Krasman, 2014; Martínez-León and Martínez-García, 2011; Ouksel and Vyhmeister, 2000). Ouksel and Vyhmeister (2000) report that information is consequently filtered in firms with many reporting levels and as a consequence employees in lower levels of the hierarchy do not get information of the totality. Martínez-León and Martínez-García (2011) report that firms with many reporting levels are less conducive to effective learning due to high work division encouraging specialization. Some previous studies suggest that less complex (flat) organisations perform better than more complex (tall) ones (such as Carillo and Kopelman, 1991; Ivancevich and Donnelly, 1975). Some other previous studies found a negative relationship between reporting levels and work performance (such as Carzo and Yanouzas,

1969; Martínez-León and Martínez-García, 2011; Meltzer and Salter, 1960). In a laboratory experiment, Carzo and Yanouzas (1969) found that the amount of time taken to process decisions, resolve conflict and coordinate effort are longer when an organization has many reporting levels. Krasman (2014) stated that firms with a wider span of control in flatter structures may lead subordinates to perceive being left alone and this can be taken into granted by them in a positive manner that lead to creativity. Martínez-León and Martínez-García (2011) suggest that since firms with a fewer reporting levels are formed of top managers, strategic groups and multidisciplinary teams, vertical decision making is replaced by horizontal collaboration in such firms leading to better performance outcomes. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H4: Team process will be less satisfying when many reporting levels exist in the firm

Methodology

Measures

An individual's perceived opportunities for promotion were measured by three items that inquired the self-evaluation of opportunities received so far and perceived future opportunities. These items were developed based on insights gained from previous studies, such as opportunities for promotion (Groot and van den Brink, 1996; James & Jones, 1974) and opportunities for growth and advancement (Groot and van den Brink, 1996; Manning, 2010).

An individual's perceived opportunities for lateral transfer were measured by three items that inquired the self-evaluation of opportunities received so far and perceived future opportunities. These items were developed based on insights gained from previous studies, such as receipt of different positions in the organisation without changes in hierarchy and

salary (Huang, 1999), scheduled non-merit upgrades (Acosta, 2010), and rotating employees across job positions (Schaefer et al., 1979).

An individual's satisfaction with work environment was measured by three items that inquired overall self-evaluation of the environment of workplace. These items were developed based on insights gained from previous studies, such as awareness of needs and problems (Groot and van den Brink, 1996), responds to needs and problems (Groot and van den Brink, 1996), interaction facilitation (Manning, 2010), and the development of mutually satisfying relationships within the team (James & Jones, 1974).

An individual's self-evaluation of team process was measured by six items that inquired psychosocial outcomes of team work environment such as the degree of experienced friendliness, support, and ability to cope. These items were developed based on insights gained from previous studies, such as the formalization of decision-making process (Bourgault et al., 2008), the quality of decision-making process (Bourgault et al., 2008), ability to cope by team members (Staples & Webster, 2007), intention to remain on the team (Staples & Webster, 2007), team effectiveness in performing tasks (Bourgault et al., 2008; Staples & Webster, 2007), and the frustration and alienation of team members (Wageman et al., 2005). All the items used in the present study to measure the four variables are given in Table 3. All these item measures were on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high).

The present study operationalized reporting levels under two groups, where few reporting levels to be two levels and many reporting levels to be 3 to 5 levels. This operationalization was based on three reasons, namely a) after an extensive review of previous studies (such as Meltzer & Salter, 1960; Porter & Lawler, 1964; Urwick, 1956; Worthy, 1950), Carzo and Yanouzas (1969) proposed a classification where flat structure to have two levels and tall structure to have four reporting levels within any given organization's

size category, b) recent studies reviewed earlier (such as Grant, et al., 2010; Turner & Keegan, 1999; Oldham & Hackman, 2010; Osterman, 2010) suggest that contemporary work organizations tend to be more flatter than otherwise, worldwide, and c) previous studies conducted in the Sri Lankan ICT sector (such as Liyanaarachchi, 2011; Wickramasinghe, 2009) suggest that firms have very limited layers in the hierarchy (to represent top management and technical specialists) irrespective of the number of employees fulltime engaged. Hence, it is possible to presume that although Carzo and Yanouzas (1969) classification is several decades old, it may still reflect contemporary work context.

In addition to the above mentioned main variables, data were collected on seven characteristics to describe the sample. These were the years of business existence of the firm, the existence of a promotional ladder, the number of members in the team of each respondent, age, sex, education, and the tenure of respondents.

Sample

A random sample of respondents engaged full-time in team work environment in the Sri Lankan ICT sector was selected. During the past decade ICT sector of the country grown exponentially leading to a growth of a professional and technical middle class in Sri Lanka (Flecker and Huws, 2003). The firms in this new sector are reputed to employ educated and trained employees (Sri Lanka ICT Association, 2007; World Bank, 2006). All most all firms hire people with bachelor's degrees for their entry level jobs (Liyanaarachchi, 2011). This fact is reflected in our sample, where 90 per cent of respondents have post-graduate qualification (refer to Table 1). The firms belong to ICT sector was identified through online directories available in the country. Initial contacts were made over the telephone using the simple random sampling method. Second, contact persons were identified with the help of human resource personnel in each firm. Contact persons from each firm together with the

author of this paper selected a random sample of employees covering not more than 5 per cent of employees from a single firm. These respondents were in job positions of entry level to middle level of the hierarchy. However, attempts were not made in the study to differentiate responses from each responding firm since it was not the intention. Of the 600 self-administered questionnaires distributed, 289 respondents belong to 43 firms responded voluntarily within three weeks of initial distribution of the questionnaire. A total of 281 usable responses resulted in a 47% response rate. With regard to respondents, 49.6% came from firms with 2 levels of reporting while 50.4% came from firms with 3-5 levels of reporting. Respondents' characteristics and the results of chi-square and independent sample t-test for any differences by reporting levels are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. The results shown in Table 1 and 2 suggest that there are no significant differences in sample respondents by the number of reporting levels of the firm.

Table 1 about here

Table 2 about here

Method of data collection and analysis

The self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. The questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample of employees that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution. The pre-tested survey questionnaire after amendments was administered among the respondents. The cover letter sent to participants together with the self-administered survey questionnaire briefed the aims of the study, and assured their confidentiality by allowing them to respond anonymously.

The data were tested for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity, and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias. Data were analysed using the software package for social sciences (SPSS). In addition to descriptive statistics, chi-square test, independent sample t-test, and logistic regression were used appropriately to explore differences across groups. For logistic regression, “2 reporting levels” is coded as “0” and “3-5 reporting levels” is coded as “1”; “2 reporting levels” was defined as the “first category” in logistic regression.

Results and discussion

The measures of opportunities for promotion, opportunities for lateral transfer, satisfaction with team process, and satisfaction with work environment were, first, subjected to reliability analysis. Second, exploratory factor analysis (with Varimax rotation) was conducted as a data reduction technique to identify factors that underlie the item measures to be used in the subsequent analysis. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues should be greater than 1; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach’s alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be 0.7. Third, for each variable, average variance extracted (AVE) and construct reliability (CR) were calculated. Table 3 summarises the results of these analyses.

Table 3 about here

Results of t-test for opportunities for promotion, opportunities for lateral transfer, satisfaction with team process, and satisfaction with work environment are shown in Table 4. The results suggest that there are significant differences in opportunities for promotion and

satisfaction with work environment by the number of reporting levels. Specifically, opportunities for promotion are higher in firms with 3-5 levels; the difference is significant ($t = 2.728, p < 0.01$). Satisfaction with work environment is higher in firms with 2 levels; the difference is significant ($t = -2.203, p < 0.05$).

Table 4 about here

The correlations between variables are shown in Table 5. As can be seen in Table 5, satisfaction with work environment significantly negatively correlate with reporting levels ($p < 0.05$) while opportunities for promotion significantly positively correlate with reporting levels ($p < .01$).

Table 5 about here

To evaluate the effect of reporting levels on opportunities for promotion, opportunities for lateral transfer, team process, and satisfaction with work environment logistic regression was performed. In the stage 1 of the data analysis all four dependent variables were entered into the model. The non-significance chi-square value of 117.52 of Pearson statistic and 205.94 of deviance statistic suggested a good fit. The -2 Log-likelihood value was 199.23 ($p < .01$). However, the Likelihood Ratio Tests for individual model parameters suggested that opportunities for lateral transfer and team process were not significant. These findings do not support H2 and H4. Therefore, these two variables were dropped based on the preference for more parsimonious reduced model, and proceeded to the stage 2 of the analysis.

In the stage 2 of the analysis, the non-significance chi-square value of 27.99 of Pearson statistic and 36.09 of deviance statistic suggested a good fit. A significant -2 Log-likelihood value of 80.48 suggests ($p < .01$) that predictors were significantly related to the number of reporting levels. The Likelihood Ratio Tests for individual model parameters suggested that both opportunities for promotion and satisfaction with work environment were significant. These findings support H1 and H3. The summarised results of stage 2 of the data analysis are shown in Table 6. It is evident from Table 6 that opportunities for promotion and satisfaction with work environment are important variables that discriminate between the number of reporting levels. Specifically, the log odds of an employee to be in a firm with 3-5 reporting levels (as oppose to 2 levels) with more opportunities for promotion is almost two and half times (2.45) as high. On the contrary, the log odds of an employee to be in a firm with 2 reporting levels (as oppose to 3-5 levels) with more satisfaction with work environment is almost twice (1.99) as high. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 66%.

Table 6 about here

Conclusions and implications

The paper presented empirical findings for the differential effects of reporting levels on employees working in team work environment in terms of opportunities for promotion, opportunities for lateral transfer, satisfaction with work environment, and satisfaction with team process. The findings supported the hypotheses that employees perceive more opportunities for promotion when there are many reporting levels (3-5 levels in the present

study) whereas they perceive more satisfaction with the work environment when there are few reporting levels (2 levels in the present study).

The findings have implications for both theory and practice. With regard to implications for the literature, first, the findings of the present study corroborate the findings of previous studies (e.g., Blau, 1968; Porter & Lawler, 1964) that found organizations with many reporting levels tend to provide more opportunities for promotion than organizations at the opposite-end. In a similar vein, the findings of the present study corroborate the findings of previous studies (e.g., Ghiselli & Johnson, 1970; Ivancevich & Donnelly, 1975; Porter & Lawler, 1964; Worthy, 1950) that found organizations with few reporting levels tend to provide more satisfying work environment for employees than organizations at the opposite-end. However, it should be noted that previous studies were conducted several decades ago (e.g., Blau, 1968; Porter & Lawler, 1964), and during the past two decades employment landscape has changed and new expert occupational groups have emerged in fields such as ICT and incumbents of these new occupations are identified as knowledge workers. Hence, the context of previous studies and the present study is different due to the fact that present study is conducted in the work contexts that emerged recently; employees are in team work environment. In this context, the findings make an important contribution to the literature by providing empirical evidence in contemporary team work context, where employees tend to have more opportunities for promotion when the structure is relatively tall with several reporting levels while they tend to be more satisfied with the work environment when the structure is relatively flat with few reporting levels.

Second, the literature suggests that organizations with certain structural properties (such as reporting levels) attract and/or select employees with particular personal attributes (e.g., Oldham & Hackman, 1981). However, the findings of the present study do not support this argument since differential effects of reporting levels on age, sex and education were not

significant (refer to Table 1 and 2). This may be due to the fact that the business sector investigated in the study is relatively new (young) and as a result job positions in this sector are mainly filled with young people, with relatively homogeneous characteristics (refer to Table 1 and 2).

With regard to implications for practice, the number of reporting levels shows the division of work, authority, and the internal pattern of relationships within an organization. The findings imply, on the one hand, the need of maintaining a hierarchy with several reporting levels to create a promotional ladder for employees in team work environment. On the other hand, there is a need of maintaining a hierarchy with few reporting levels for employees to be satisfied with the work environment. Hence, findings of the study appear to have implications for managerial decision making in finding a breakeven to fulfil these two conflicting needs.

Finally, the validation of a measure requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence, future researches, in different samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that complement questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. Further, the present study was confined to investigate the effects of vertical complexity, which is one of the structural characteristics of any organization's anatomy that provide the structural foundation within which an organization functions. However, it is argued that these structural characteristics could be manipulated to create high-performing, satisfying organizations (e.g., Cummings and Berger, 1976). Therefore, future research could widen the scope by investigating combined effects of reporting levels with other non-structural characteristics such as training and advancement opportunities on employees. Last but not least, data on reporting levels were collected a categorical scale. Future studies could obtain ratio scale data for better prediction.

References

- Acosta, P. (2010). Promotion dynamics the Peter Principle: Incumbents vs. external hires. *Labour Economics*, 17(6), 975–986.
- Andersen, J.A., & Jonsson, P. (2006). Does organization structure matter? On the relationship between the structure, functioning and effectiveness. *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, 3(3), 237–263.
- Blau, P.M. (1968). The hierarchy of authority in organizations. *American Journal of Sociology*, 73, 453-467.
- Bourgault, M., Drouin, N., & Hamel, E. (2008). Decision making within distributed project teams: an exploration of formalization and autonomy as determinants of success. *Project Management Journal*, 39(Supplement), S97–S110.
- Carillo, P.M., & Kopelman, R.E. (1991). Organization structure and productivity effects of subunit size, vertical complexity and administrative intensity on operational efficiency. *Group & Organization Studies*, 16(1), 44-59.
- Carzo, R. Jr., & Yanouzas, J.N. (1969). Effects of flat and tall organization. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 14, 178-191.
- Cummings, L.L., & Berger, C.J. (1976). Organization structure: How does it influence attitudes and performance? *Organizational Dynamics*, 5(2), 34-49.
- Dalton, D.R., Todor, W.D., Spendolini, W.J., Fielding, G.J., & Porter, L.W. (1980). Organization structure and performance: A critical review. *Academy of Management Review*, 5(1), 49-64.
- Flecker, J., & Huws, U. (2003). *Asian Emergence: The World's Back Office?*, The Institute for Employment Studies, Brighton.
- Ghiselli, E.E., & Johnson, D.A. (1970). Need satisfaction, managerial success, and organizational structure. *Personnel Psychology*, 23, 569–576.
- Grant, A.M., Fried, Y., Parker, S.K., & Frese, M. (2010). Putting job design in context: Introduction to the special issue. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31, 145-157.
- Groot, W., & van den Brink, H.M. (1996). Glass ceilings or dead ends: job promotion of men and women compared, *Economic Letters*, 53, 221-226.

- Haas, M.R. (2010). The double-edged swords of autonomy and external knowledge: Analyzing team effectiveness in a multinational organization. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(5), 989–1008.
- Huang, H.J. (1999). Job rotation from the employees' point of view. *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management*, 7(1), 75-85.
- Inzerilli, G., & Laurent, A. (1983). Managerial views of organization structure in France and the USA. *International studies of management and organization*, 13(1-2), 97-118.
- Ivancevich, J.M., & Donnelly, J.H. (1975). Relations of organizational structure to job satisfaction, anxiety, stress, and performance. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 20, 272-280.
- Iverson, R.D., & Roy, P. (1994). A causal model of behavioral commitment: Evidence from a study of Australian blue-collar employees. *Journal of Management*, 20, 15-41.
- Jackson, J.H., & Morgan, C.P. (1982). *Organization Theory*. Second Edition, London: Prentice-Hall.
- Jacob, N. (2007). Organizational structure and cross-cultural management: The case of credit Suisse's Project Copernicus in Singapore. *Vikalpa*, 32(4), 63-73.
- James, L.R., & Jones, A.P. (1974). Organizational climate: A review of theory and research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 81, 1096-1112.
- Krasman, J. (2014). Do my staff trust me? *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 35, 470 – 488.
- Liyanaarachchi, L.A.L.S. (2011). A study on differences between job description and actual jobs performed by engineers in voice telecommunications sector in Sri Lanka. Unpublished MBA dissertation, University of Moratuwa.
- Manning, R.L. (2010). Development of the psychological climate scale for small business. *Journal of New Business Ideas & Trends*, 8(1), 50-65.
- Martínez-León, I.M., & Martínez-García, J.A. (2011). The influence of organizational structure on organizational learning. *International Journal of Manpower*, 32(5/6), 537 – 566.
- Meltzer, L., & Salter, J. (1960). Organizational structure, and the performance and job satisfactions of physiologists. *American Sociological Review*, 27, 351-362.

- Oldham, G.R., & Hackman, J.R. (1981). Relationships between organizational structure and employee reactions: Comparing alternative frameworks. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 26, 66- 83.
- Oldham, G.R., & Hackman, J.R. (2010). Not what it was and not what it will be: The future of job design research. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31, 463-479.
- Osterman, P. (2010). Job design in the context of the job market. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31, 401-411.
- Ouksel, A., & Vyhmeister, R. (2000). Performance of organizational design models and their impact on organization learning. *Computational & Mathematical Organization Theory*, 6(4), pp. 395-410.
- Parker, S.K., Wall, T.D., & Cordery, J.L. (2001). Future work design research and practice: towards an elaborated model of work design. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 74, 413-440.
- Peters, L., & Karren, R.J. (2009). An examination of the roles of trust and functional diversity on virtual team performance ratings. *Group & Organization Management*, 34(4), 479-504.
- Peters, L.H., Greer, C.R., & Youngblood, S.A. (2000). *The Blackwell Encyclopedic Dictionary of Human Resource Management*, Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishers.
- Porter, L.W., & Lawler, E.E. III. (1964). The effects of ‘tall’ versus ‘flat’ organization structures on managerial satisfaction. *Personnel Psychology*, 17, 135-148.
- Schaefer, M.E., Massey, F.A., & Hermanson, R.H. (1979). The Peter Principle revisited: An economic perspective. *Human Resource Management*, 1-6.
- Spilerman, S., & Lunde, T. (1991). Features of educational attainment and job promotion prospects. *American Journal of Sociology*, 97(3), 689-720.
- Sri Lanka ICT Association (2007). *Rising Demand: The Increasing Demand for IT Workers Spells a Challenging Opportunity for the IT Industry-National IT Workforce Survey*, Sri Lanka ICT Association, Colombo.
- Staples, D.S., & Webster, J. (2007). Exploring traditional and virtual team members’ “best practices”: A social cognitive theory perspective. *Small Group Research*, 38(1), 60-97.
- Turner, J.R., & Keegan, A.E. (1999). The versatile project-based organization: Governance and operational control. *European Management Journal*, 17(3), 296–309.
- Urwick, L.F. (1956). The manager’s span of control. *Harvard Business Review*, 34, 39-47.

Wageman, R., Hackman, J. R., & Lehman, E. (2005). Team diagnostic survey: Development of an instrument. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 41(4), 373-398.

Wickramasinghe, V. (2009). Predictors of job satisfaction among IT graduates in offshore outsourced IT firms. *Personnel Review*, 38(4), 413-431.

World Bank (2006). *Offshore to Sri Lanka: Finding Sri Lanka's offshoring niche*. World Bank South Asia Finance and Private Sector Development Unit, World Bank, Colombo.

Worthy, J.C. (1950). Organizational structure and employee morale. *American Sociological Review*, 15, 169-179.

Tables

TABLE 1. RESPONDENT CHARACTERISTICS AND RESULTS OF CHI-SQUARE

	Total (n = 281)	Reporting levels [†]		Pearson Chi-Square
		2 levels (n = 132)	3-5 levels (n = 149)	
Sex [†] :				4.35 (p > .05)
Male	77%	75%	80%	
Female	33%	25	20	
The highest level of education [†] :				6.28 (p > .05)
Diploma	7%	70%	67%	
Bachelor's degree	3%	10%	12%	
Postgraduate degree	90%	20%	21%	
Number of members in team [†] :				4.69 (p > .05)
Less than 5	24%	23%	25%	
5 to 10	54%	55%	51%	
More than 10	22%	22%	24%	
Existence of promotional ladder [†] :				1.25 (p > .05)
Yes	70%	64%	76%	
No	30%	36%	24%	
Years of business existence [†] :				3.65 (p > .05)
Less than 5 years	28%	29%	27%	
5-10 years	47%	48%	46%	
10-15 years	25%	23%	27%	

Note: [†] Data obtained on categorical scale

TABLE 2. RESPONDENT CHARACTERISTICS AND RESULTS OF INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST

	Total Mean	Reporting levels [†]		t-test
		2 levels Mean	3-5 levels Mean	
Age [◇]	29.02	28.67	28.58	5.43 (p > .05)
Experience in the present workplace [◇]	3.23	2.80	2.76	3.98 (p > .05)
Total work experience [◇]	5.42	4.61	5.17	2.62 (p > .05)

Note: [◇] Data obtained on ratio scale, [†] Data obtained on categorical scale

TABLE 3. SUMMARISED RESULTS: FACTOR ANALYSIS

	Estimates
<i>Opportunities for promotion:</i>	
In your current job, the level of opportunities you had for promotion	.802
In your current job, the level of opportunities you may have for a promotion within next three years	.769
Overall, the level of satisfaction you have to advance to a higher rank within the organizational hierarchy	.742
Explained variation	64%
Eigenvalue	3.17
Cronbach's alpha	.755
AVE	.60
CR	.81
<i>Opportunities for lateral transfer:</i>	
In your current job, your experience of increase in roles and responsibilities without changes in hierarchical level	.783
In your current job, the level of opportunities you may have for lateral transfers within next three years	.732
Overall, the level of satisfaction you have to move to a number of different positions without changes in hierarchical level	.709
Explained variation	67%
Eigenvalue	2.22
Cronbach's alpha	.732
AVE	.55
CR	.78
<i>Satisfaction with work environment:</i>	
Encouragement for the development of mutually satisfying relationships between employees	.759
The level of cooperation between your work team and other work teams	.711
Overall, rate your evaluation of the supportiveness of the work environment	.701
Explained variation	72%
Eigenvalue	1.79
Cronbach's alpha	.806
AVE	.52
CR	.77
<i>Satisfaction with team process:</i>	
Level of importance of the individuals as team members	.837
Level of solidarity within the team	.841
Level of participation in the decision-making process	.792
Level of innovative ideas coming up during team discussions	.772
Level of tolerance of new ideas within the team	.728
Level of collective decision-making within the team	.714
Explained variation	73%
Eigenvalue	1.54
Cronbach's alpha	.849
AVE	.61
CR	.90

TABLE 4. DIFFERENCES BY THE NUMBER OF REPORTING LEVELS

	2 levels		3-5 levels		t value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	
Opportunities for promotion	2.38	.62	2.89	.80	2.728**
Opportunities for lateral transfer	3.07	.72	3.02	.64	.170
Satisfaction with work environment	3.81	.86	3.54	.79	-2.203*
Satisfaction with team process	3.70	.47	3.68	.46	.247

Note: * p < 0.05 and ** p < 0.01.

TABLE 5. CORRELATIONS

	1	2	3	4	5
1 Satisfaction with work environment	.77				
2 Opportunities for promotion	.211*	.74			
3 Opportunities for lateral transfer	.114	.156*	.72		
4 Satisfaction with team process	.164*	.133*	.125*	.78	
5 No. of reporting levels	-.185*	.261**	.006	.021	-

Notes: * p < 0.05 and ** p < 0.01; diagonal entries denote square root of AVE (where applicable); off-diagonal entries denote correlations between constructs.

TABLE 6. SUMMARISED RESULTS (AT STAGE II): LOGISTIC REGRESSION

	B	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Opportunities for promotion	.837	7.608	.006	2.448
Satisfaction with work environment	-.702	6.391	.011	1.996

Note: The reference category is: 1-2 levels.

Variables in the equation: reporting levels (data obtained on categorical scale), opportunities for promotion and satisfaction with work environment (5 point Likert-scales).